

MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION ARTICLE MODERN VIEWS

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Annotation. Myocardial infarction (MI), colloquially known as "heart attack," is caused by decreased or complete cessation of blood flow to a portion of the myocardium. Myocardial infarction may be "silent," and go undetected, or it could be a catastrophic event leading to hemodynamic deterioration and sudden death. Most myocardial infarctions are due to underlying coronary artery disease, the leading cause of death in the United States. With coronary artery occlusion, the myocardium is deprived of oxygen. Prolonged deprivation of oxygen supply to the myocardium can lead to myocardial cell death and necrosis. Patients can present with chest discomfort or pressure that can radiate to the neck, jaw, shoulder, or arm. In addition to the history and physical exam, myocardial ischemia may be associated with ECG changes and elevated biochemical markers such as cardiac troponins. This activity describes the pathophysiology, evaluation, and management of myocardial infarction and highlights the role of the interprofessional team in improving care for affected patients.

Keywords: myocardial infarction, clinic, diagnosis, treatment

Myocardial infarction (MI), colloquially known as "heart attack," is caused by decreased or complete cessation of blood flow to a portion of the myocardium. Myocardial infarction may be "silent" and go undetected, or it could be a catastrophic event leading to hemodynamic deterioration and sudden death.^[1] Most myocardial infarctions are due to underlying coronary artery disease, the leading cause of death in the United States. With coronary artery occlusion, the myocardium is deprived of oxygen. Prolonged deprivation of oxygen supply to the myocardium can lead to myocardial cell death and necrosis.^[2] Patients can present with chest discomfort or pressure that can radiate to the neck, jaw, shoulder, or arm. In addition to the history and physical exam, myocardial ischemia may be associated with ECG changes and elevated biochemical markers such as cardiac troponins.^{[3][4]}

As stated above, myocardial infarction is closely associated with coronary artery disease. INTERHEART is an international multi-center case-control study which delineated the following modifiable risk factors for coronary artery disease:^{[5][6]}

1. Smoking
2. Abnormal lipid profile/blood apolipoprotein (raised ApoB/ApoA1)
3. Hypertension
4. Diabetes mellitus
5. Abdominal obesity (waist/hip ratio) (greater than 0.90 for males and greater than 0.85 for females)
6. Psychosocial factors such as depression, loss of the locus of control, global stress, financial stress, and life events including marital separation, job loss, and family conflicts
7. Lack of daily consumption of fruits or vegetables
8. Lack of physical activity
9. Alcohol consumption (weaker association, protective)

The INTERHEART study showed that all the above risk factors were significantly associated with acute myocardial infarction except for alcohol consumption, which showed a weaker association. Smoking and abnormal apolipoprotein ratio showed the strongest association

with acute myocardial infarction. The increased risk associated with diabetes and hypertension were found to be higher in women, and the protective effect of exercise and alcohol was also found to be higher in women.^[5] The most common cause of death and disability in the western world and worldwide is coronary artery disease.^[11] Based on 2015 mortality data from the National Health Interview Survey (NHIS-CDC), MI mortality was 114,023, and MI any-mention mortality (i.e., MI is mentioned as a contributing factor in the death certificate) was 151,863. As per the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES)-CDC data from 2011 to 2014, an estimated 16.5 million Americans older than 20 years of age have coronary artery disease, and the prevalence was higher in males than females for all ages. As per the NHANES 2011 through 2014, the overall prevalence of MI is 3.0% in US adults older than 20 years of age.

Prevalence of MI in the US Sub-populations

Non-Hispanic Whites

- 4.0% (Male)
- 2.4% (Female)

Non-Hispanic Blacks

- 3.3% (Male)
- 2.2% (Female)

Hispanics

- 2.9% (Male)
- 2.1% (Female)

Non-Hispanic Asians

- 2.6% (Male)
- 0.7% (Female)

Based on the Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities Study (ARIC) performed by National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute (NHLBI) collected between 2005 and 2014, the estimated annual incidence is 605,000 new MIs and 200,000 recurrent MIs.^[12]

The ARIC study also found that the average age at first MI is 65.6 years for males and 72.0 years for females. In the past decades, several studies have shown a declining incidence of MI in the United States.^[12]

Pathophysiology

The acute occlusion of one or multiple large epicardial coronary arteries for more than 20 to 40 minutes can lead to acute myocardial infarction. The occlusion is usually thrombotic and due to the rupture of a plaque formed in the coronary arteries. The occlusion leads to a lack of oxygen in the myocardium, which results in sarcolemmal disruption and myofibril relaxation.^[2] These changes are one of the first ultrastructural changes in the process of MI, which are followed by mitochondrial alterations. The prolonged ischemia ultimately results in liquefactive necrosis of myocardial tissue. The necrosis spreads from sub-endocardium to sub-epicardium. The subepicardium is believed to have increased collateral circulation, which delays its death.^[2] Depending on the territory affected by the infarction, the cardiac function is compromised. Due to the negligible regeneration capacity of the myocardium, the infarcted area heals by scar formation, and often, the heart is remodeled characterized by dilation, segmental hypertrophy of remaining viable tissue, and cardiac dysfunction.^[13]

History and Physical

The imbalance between oxygen supply and the demand leads to myocardial ischemia and can sometimes lead to myocardial infarction. The patient's history, electrocardiographic findings, and elevated serum biomarkers help identify ischemic symptoms. Myocardial ischemia can present as chest pain, upper extremity pain, mandibular, or epigastric discomfort that occurs during exertion or at rest. Myocardial ischemia can also present as dyspnea or fatigue, which are known to be ischemic equivalents.[\[14\]](#) The chest pain is usually retrosternal and is sometimes described as the sensation of pressure or heaviness. The pain often radiates to the left shoulder, neck, or arms with no obvious precipitating factors, and it may be intermittent or persistent. The pain usually lasts for more than 20 minutes.[\[15\]](#) It is usually not affected by positional changes or active movement of the region. Additional symptoms, such as sweating, nausea, abdominal pain, dyspnea, and syncope, may also be present.[\[14\]\[16\]\[17\]](#) The MI can also present atypically with subtle findings such as palpitations, or more dramatic manifestations, such as cardiac arrest. The MI can sometimes present with no symptoms.[\[18\]](#)

Evaluation

The three components in the evaluation of the MI are clinical features, ECG findings, and cardiac biomarkers.

ECG

Other risk factors include a moderately high level of plasma homocysteine, which is an independent risk factor of MI. Elevated plasma homocysteine is potentially modifiable and can be treated with folic acid, vitamin B6, and vitamin B12.[\[7\]](#)

Some non-modifiable risk factors for myocardial infarction include advanced age, male gender (males tend to have myocardial infarction earlier in life), genetics (there is an increased risk of MI if a first-degree relative has a history of cardiovascular events before the age of 50).[\[6\]\[8\]](#) The role of genetic loci that increase the risk for MI is under active investigation.[\[9\]\[10\]](#)

The resting 12 lead ECG is the first-line diagnostic tool for the diagnosis of acute coronary syndrome (ACS). It should be obtained within 10 minutes of the patient's arrival in the emergency department.[\[15\]](#) Acute MI is often associated with dynamic changes in the ECG waveform. Serial ECG monitoring can provide important clues to the diagnosis if the initial ECG is non-diagnostic at initial presentation.[\[14\]](#) Serial or continuous ECG recordings may help determine reperfusion or re-occlusion status. A large and prompt reduction in ST-segment elevation is usually seen in reperfusion.[\[14\]](#)

ECG findings suggestive of ongoing coronary artery occlusion (in the absence of left ventricular hypertrophy and bundle branch block):[\[17\]](#)

ST-segment elevation in two contiguous lead (measured at J-point) of

1. Greater than 5 mm in men younger than 40 years, greater than 2 mm in men older than 40 years, or greater than 1.5 mm in women in leads V2-V3 and/or
2. Greater than 1 mm in all other leads

ST-segment depression and T-wave changes

1. New horizontal or down-sloping ST-segment depression greater than 5 mm in 2 contiguous leads and/or T inversion greater than 1 mm in two contiguous leads with prominent R waves or R/S ratio of greater than 1

The hyperacute T-wave amplitude, with prominent symmetrical T waves in two contiguous leads, maybe an early sign of acute MI that may precede the ST-segment elevation. Other ECG

findings associated with myocardial ischemia include cardiac arrhythmias, intraventricular blocks, atrioventricular conduction delays, and loss of precordial R-wave amplitude (less specific finding).[\[18\]](#)

ECG findings alone are not sufficient to diagnose acute myocardial ischemia or acute MI as other conditions such as acute pericarditis, left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH), left bundle branch block (LBBB), Brugada syndrome, Takatsubo syndrome (TTS), and early repolarization patterns also present with ST deviation.

ECG changes associated with prior MI (in the absence of left ventricular hypertrophy and left bundle branch block):

1. Any Q wave in lead V2-V3 greater than 0.02 s or QS complex in leads V2-V3
2. Q wave > 0.3 s and greater than 1 mm deep or QS complex in leads I, II, aVL, aVF or V4-V6 in any two leads of contiguous lead grouping (I, aVL; V1-V6; II, III, aVF)

R wave > 0.04 s in V1-V2 and R/S greater than 1 with a concordant positive T wave in the absence of conduction defect.

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